

Review of *The Space of Latin American Women Modernists*. **Camilla Sutherland**. **Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2024. 264 pages. \$ 95.00 cloth. \$ 90.25, ebook.**

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By the 1920s, most Latin American nations had held centennial celebrations marking the end of colonial rule. However, even after a hundred years of independence, the debate on the countries' cultural identities had not been settled. As a Eurocentric trend, modernism (distinct from the autochthonous Azulian modernismo) was an especially polemical aspect of the debate. Camilla Sutherland's book, *The Space of Latin American Women Modernists* (LAWM) is informed by the discussions that sought to decipher Latin America's positionality in the literary and cultural trend of modernism. Sutherland spotlights eight women creators who, as pioneers

of modernism, were influential players in crafting their country's cultural landscape during the first half of the twentieth century.

While critics have formed a broad consensus on demarcating the post-modernist phase in Latin American literature and culture, the periodization of modernism has been heavily contested. However, when the views of scholars such as Donald Shaw, Mary Lee Bretz, and Enrique Pupo-Walker on modernism are coalesced, one can settle upon the period of 1920-50 as the years when modernist creators were at helm of the cultural imaginary in the Latin American continent. Sutherland's decision to select the works of modernist women creators from this period for commentary redresses the acute deficit of attention received by them from canonical critics.

Until recently, the male writers of Azulian modernismo of the 1890s to 1910s – Rubén Darío, Leopoldo Lugones, and José Enrique Rodó – have attracted the bulk of critical attention, crowding out women modernists who succeeded them. In Latin America, all named literary movements from neo-classicism of the early-nineteenth century to Boom Literature of the mid-twentieth century, exclude women from the canon. Sutherland's book examines and corrects the marginalization of women creators.

LAWM's selected writers and artists fall into two broad groups. The first group, which interpreted the world through images is comprised of the painters Frida Kahlo and Remedios Varo, printmaker, Norah Borges, and sculptor, Marina Núñez del Prado. The second group, which used the written word to represent their worldview includes Gabriela Mistral, Victoria Ocampo, Norah Lange, and María Luisa Bombal. Of these eight women, three creators are from Argentina – Ocampo, Lange, and Borges, two each from Mexico – Kahlo and Varo and Chile – Mistral and Bombal, and one - Nuñez del Prado, from Bolivia. Thus, the book is ambitious in its regional and generic scope.

Camilla Sutherland declares at the start: “This book revolves around three key terms: space, gender and modernism linked through the element of time.” She consistently teases out all three strands in the chapters of the book. Each chapter utilizes a distinct view point to examine the women creators’ spatial praxis, which became tactically important in their feminist literary-cultural strategy. The introductory chapter provides biographic information about the women and the personal bonds that they shared with one another. In some instances, such as Mistral-Ocampo’s, the enduring intellectual bond has been documented in letters that they exchanged over thirty years; in other instances such as Lange-Bombal’s, the relationship was characterised by personal affinity that extended to the professional arena – Lange au-

thored the prologue to the first edition of Bombal's first novel. Thus, Sutherland locates the women in a network of shared consciousness of their personal struggles in machista societies instead of examining their lives and work in disconnected silos.

The four thematic chapters titled "Upon the Threshold: Reconsidering the Modernist Home", "Mother Earth Remapped", "Cosmopolitan Promises: Travel, Exile and Alterity", and "'On the margins of the fray': Situating Modernist Women in Print Media" demonstrate the continuous spatial negotiation between public and private spheres that these women undertook to protect their cultural artefacts from oblivion. The first three chapters deal with the sub-themes of domesticity, fertility, cultivation, sexualization of nature, and self-exoticization.

In Chapter 1, Sutherland's attention to micro threshold spaces – window, doorframe, stair, entryway – deterritorializes these spatial elements from an ambience of private inconsequence to arenas of public prominence. Chapter 2 delves into the nature-culture question. The second chapter contrasts Vicente Huidobro's disparaging creationist gaze on nature's 'feminine' charms with the shared vulnerability with which the women creators viewed nature. Sutherland shows that for the women creators, the relationship between nature, nation and natality was crucial to articulating Latin America's literary-cultural positionality. The third chapter argues that

the women created a transnational reach for their work by their frequent travels. For example, Gabriela Mistral never returned to her native Chile once she left when she was thirty-seven years old to join the Institute for Intellectual Cooperation in Paris. She spent the latter half of her life in France, Mexico, and the United States of America. The other women also used travel to draw international acclaim for their work.

In the last chapter, Sutherland presents hard data that proves the multi-faceted marginalization of women in the print media. They were allocated only 7-10% space in literary journals. The journal *Sur*, which was founded and edited by Victoria Ocampo, one of the women creators studied in the book, was also complicit in their marginalization. Sutherland contrasts reviews of male and female writers' works to show that men often used patronizing and derisive tones while commenting on women's texts. Even when a review was not patently sexist, it would typically relegate the woman's work into relative obscurity by pointing out the 'smallness' of her vision or by including personal anecdotes that distracted attention away from the text under review. Mistral's poetry and Kahlo's paintings received backhanded praise as outcomes of excessive emotion that spilled into their art. Sutherland demonstrates that the woman creator was relegated to a confining interiority, whereas the male reviewer acted as a gatekeeper to the larger exterior that he was privileged to see.

There are a few lacunae in the book that the author could have addressed, given the ambitious scope of the work. Uruguay and its legendary modernist poets Delmira Agustini and Juana de Ibarbourou, and the iconic Uruguayan author Armonía Somers are conspicuous by their absence. Any discussion on Latin American women modernists is incomplete without some reference to the Uruguayan triad that has left a deep imprint on the Latin American literary landscape. Some aspects of analytic significance are mentioned only in passing. The thirty-year long correspondence between Gabriela Mistral and Victoria Ocampo merits spatial analysis, especially in view of the different social classes that the women came from. In one of her letters from 1939, Mistral, pointing out the class divide between the two writes:

Maybe what I miss in you is nothing but a share of common experience. The experience of poverty, of fighting, in blood and mud, with life. There's no remedy for it in this life's journey. In me there's hardness, fanaticism, ugliness, that you can't be aware of, being unaware as you are of what it's like to chew bare stones for thirty years with a woman's gums, amid hard people.

The metaphor of chewing stones with a woman's gums resonated so strongly with Ocampo that she used it almost three decades later, when she accepted the Vaccaro Prize in 1965. She was awarded the prize for dedicating

her life to promoting literature and music. In her acceptance speech, she claimed that she too had chewed stones with a woman's gums. At this point in her life, Ocampo had spent three weeks as a political prisoner in a Buenos Aires jail. The same city where presidents and famous intellectuals had sat down at her family dinner table every week also held the prison where she shared a cell with other women inmates. The fission of privilege that separated Mistral and Ocampo did not become an insurmountable frontier because they acknowledged it and built bridges over it. A spatial analysis of these cross-over journeys would have brought out a significant aspect of these women's alterities, which were anchored not only in their gender but also in their social classes.

Camilla Sutherland's *The Space of Latin American Women Modernists* is an important contribution to spatial literary and cultural criticism. The book also greatly aids a clear understanding of Latin American modernism as a critical evolutionary phase in trans-national gender consciousness.

